

Is Germany experiencing urban or suburban growth? Contrasting three different urbanization classifications

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Abstract. Recent accounts of urbanization and suburbanization trends relying on administrative geographical units have been criticized for not capturing the nuances of the urban-rural gradient. In this context, methods based on remotely sensed data have proven valuable for assessing the share of urban land at a high spatial resolution. Yet, such methods have rarely been used for population analysis along the urban-rural gradient. This paper addresses these issues by exploring how classifying the urban gradient alters findings on urban, suburban, and peri-urban population change trends. For this, we contrast a recently proposed urban gradient classification based on urban morphological data with a population density-focused and a functional classification. The different urban gradient classifications are applied to gridded and administrative census population data to analyze urban and suburban population change trends in German metropolitan regions from 2011 to 2022.

Submission Type. Analysis, Theory

BoK Concepts. Analytical Methods, Spatial Statistics

Keywords. urbanization, suburbanization, MAUP, population grids

Data and Software Availability: Data will be made available on request.

Extended Abstract

In an increasingly urbanizing world, population dynamics in metropolitan regions have been identified as necessary in understanding sustainable spatial planning, such as land-use efficiency and efficient service delivery. Population shifts *within* urban agglomerations have been described as cycles of ‘urbanization’, ‘suburbanization’, ‘counter-urbanization’, and ‘re-urbanization’ (van den Berg et al., 1982). What many of these accounts of (re-)urbanization and suburbanization shifts have in common is their reliance on administrative definitions of urban, suburban, and rural areas in combination with census or register data. Amcoff (2006) showed how changes in urban delimitations can alter population change measures significantly. He suggested that fine-grained population data and geographic delimitations are needed to study urban growth and expansion. The challenge of urbanization classification for empirical research along the urban-rural gradient persists in more recent work (Sander, 2018) and is a variation of the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP). This study will tackle this problem by investigating differences in population changes, particularly in suburbanization, across three urbanization classifications in German metropolitan areas.

Empirically, recent advances in fine-scale geo-referenced data allow us to capture alternative classifications of the

urban-rural gradient. For morphological definitions, remote sensing data, such as information on built-up land, provides another avenue for defining the urban-rural gradient, including suburban areas. While some of these approaches do establish direct ties to population data (Cottineau et al., 2017; De Bellefon et al., 2021; Taubenböck et al., 2022), morphological approaches are rarely systematically compared to other types of urbanization classifications. In general, these approaches do not systematically compare multiple existing urbanization classifications. Notable exceptions do exist (Balk et al., 2019, 2018; Leyk et al., 2019a; Uhl et al., 2020). For example, Leyk et al. (2019a) compared population counts within Metropolitan Statistical Areas (MSA) in the United States, using the census-designated classification of 'urban' and 'rural' and a custom classification of administrative units based on a built-up threshold. Their analysis shows how the introduction of built-up thresholds can easily reduce the number of census-classified urban populations by millions. It has to be noted that the fitness-for-use of global estimation datasets of buildings or population for research applications is still being evaluated (Leyk et al., 2019b; Uhl et al., 2020).

Given the ambiguity in empirical evidence and its potential dependence on zonation effects, this paper investigates the effect of applying three contrasting urbanization classifications on our understanding of urban and suburban population change in metropolitan areas. The different classifications of the degree of urbanization are applied to gridded and administrative census population data to analyze urbanization and suburbanization trends in Germany from 2011 to 2022. We contrast three conceptually different approaches to defining the urban-rural gradient: The Urban Ring Model, a recently proposed urban gradient classification based on an exhaustive model of 3D-building volumes, serves as a morphology-based classification (Standfuß et al., 2023); the *Degree of Urbanisation* serves as a population density-focused classification (Schiavina et al., 2023); and the German City Region classification (*Großstadtregionen*), based on population and commuting data (BBSR, 2023), serves as a functional classification of the urban gradient.

Results indicate that at the national scale, population change processes in urban, suburban, and peri-urban areas hold across classifications of the urban gradient. We detect higher urban than suburban growth for Germany and most of the 50 German metropolitan regions analyzed in this study, independent of the classification used. Isolating the effect of the urban gradient classification on population change per region statistically, we find, on average, an up to 2.48 percentage points higher urban growth rate when using the spatially more exclusive

classification approach based on morphological data compared to the other two approaches. These findings highlight the importance of classification choices for conclusions about urban metrics and the potential of morphology-based approaches to uncover urban phenomena. The methods presented in this paper can also be applied to other geographical contexts for which similar data are available.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have not used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript.

Acknowledgements.

This work was partially funded by the German Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community under the project 'Neue fernerkundungsbasierte, siedlungsstrukturelle Gebietseinheiten zur Analyse kleinräumiger Bevölkerungsentwicklung in Deutschland.'

References

- Amcoff, J., 2006. The Importance of Geographic Data Compilation Units in Monitoring Metropolitan Versus Nonmetropolitan or Urban Versus Rural Population Change. *Urban Geography* 27, 757–767. <https://doi.org/10.2747/0272-3638.27.8.757>
- Balk, D., Leyk, S., Jones, B., Montgomery, M.R., Clark, A., 2018. Understanding urbanization: A study of census and satellite-derived urban classes in the United States, 1990-2010. *PLoS One* 13, 0208487. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0208487>
- Balk, D., Montgomery, M., Engin, H., Lin, N., Major, E., Jones, B., 2019. Urbanization in India: Population and Urban Classification Grids for 2011. *Data* 4, 35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/data4010035>
- BBSR, 2023. Großstadtregionen. Available here: https://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/DE/forschung/raumb_eobachtung/Raumabgrenzungen/deutschland/regionen/Grossstadtregionen/Grossstadtregionen.html
- Cottineau, C., Hatna, E., Arcaute, E., Batty, M., 2017. Diverse cities or the systematic paradox of Urban Scaling Laws. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 63, 80–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenurbsys.2016.04.006>
- De Bellefon, M.-P., Combes, P.-P., Duranton, G., Gobillon, L., Gorin, C., 2021. Delineating urban areas using building density. *Journal of Urban Economics* 125, 103226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jue.2019.103226>

- Leyk, S., Balk, D., Jones, B., Montgomery, M.R., Engin, H., 2019a. The heterogeneity and change in the urban structure of metropolitan areas in the United States, 1990-2010. *Sci Data* 6, 321. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0329-6>
- Leyk, S., Gaughan, A.E., Adamo, S.B., Sherbinin, A., Balk, D., Freire, S., Rose, A., Stevens, F.R., Blankespoor, B., Frye, C., Comenetz, J., Sorichetta, A., MacManus, K., Pistoletti, L., Levy, M., Tatem, A.J., Pesaresi, M., 2019b. The spatial allocation of population: a review of large-scale gridded population data products and their fitness for use. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 11, 1385–1409. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-11-1385-2019>
- Sander, N., 2018. Germany: Internal migration within a changing nation, in: Champion, T., Cooke, T., Shuttleworth, I. (Eds.), *Internal Migration in the Developed World: Are We Becoming Less Mobile?*, International Population Studies. Routledge, London, pp. 226–241.
- Schiavina, M., Melchiorri, M., Pesaresi, M., 2023. GHS-SMOD R2023A - GHS settlement layers, application of the Degree of Urbanisation methodology (stage I) to GHS-POP R2023A and GHS-BUILT-S R2023A, multitemporal (1975-2030). <https://doi.org/10.2905/A0DF7A6F-49DE-46EA-9BDE-563437A6E2BA>
- Standfuß, I., Weigand, M., Gähler, M., Milbert, A., Dosch, F., Eichfuss, S., Sander, N., Geiß, C., Taubenböck, H., 2023. Categorizing urban areas into “core”, “fringe”, and “periphery” based on the built-up morphology, in: 2023 Joint Urban Remote Sensing Event (JURSE). Presented at the 2023 Joint Urban Remote Sensing Event (JURSE), IEEE, Heraklion, Greece, pp. 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JURSE57346.2023.10144133>
- Taubenböck, H., Droin, A., Standfuß, I., Dosch, F., Sander, N., Milbert, A., Eichfuss, S., Wurm, M., 2022. To be, or not to be ‘urban’? A multi-modal method for the differentiated measurement of the degree of urbanization. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 95, 101830. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2022.101830>
- Uhl, J.H., Zoraghein, H., Leyk, S., Balk, D., Corbane, C., Syrris, V., Florczyk, A.J., 2020. Exposing the urban continuum: implications and cross-comparison from an interdisciplinary perspective. *International Journal of Digital Earth* 13, 22–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2018.1550120>
- van den Berg, L., Drewett, R., Klaassen, L.H., Rossi, A., Vijverberg, C.H.T., 1982. *Urban Europe: A Study of Growth and Decline*, 1st ed. ed. Pergamon Press, Oxford ; New York.